

In low temperature areas, some farmers prefer panicle weight type rice because panicles are harvested individually. The 1981 International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery (IRCTN) planted in Korea was analyzed to determine if high yields result from high panicle number or large spikelet number per panicle.

High yields resulted from high panicle number (10-12/hill) (Table 1). However, both panicle weight and panicle number types can produce large yields. Suweon 306 and IR9129-169-3-2-3-3 yielded high because they had many panicles per hill

Table 2. Grain yield, number of panicles per hill, and number of spikelets per panicle of high yielding IRCTN entries. Chuncheon, Korea, 1981.

Entry	Yield (t/ha)	Panicle number	Total spikelets	Fertility (%)	Flowering date
T1668	7.16	6.0	196	91	1 Aug
Barkat	6.18	8.2	150	89	28 Jul
IR15924-265-3	8.94	8.2	135	84	18 Aug
IR9224-K1	9.49	13.0	140	95	31 Jul
AC3828	8.63	13.0	127	94	5 Aug
C11561-1	8.05	13.4	112	95	11 Aug
IR9129-169-3-2-3-3	6.18	17.0	124	84	7 Aug
Suweon 306	6.86	18.4	115	76	18 Aug

(Table 2). T1668 and Barkat, from mountain regions, produced large yields from big panicles. IR9224-K1, an IRRI

line reselected in Kashmir, India, has high panicle and spikelet numbers and yielded the highest.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Testing for sheath blight resistance in rice

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Rice sheath blight (ShB), caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn [*Thanetophorus cucumeris* (Frank) Donk.], occurs during wet season in parts of Kerala, Andhra Pradesh (A. P.), and West Bengal. In 1979 a severe outbreak occurred on BPT1235 and MTU6024 in West Godavari district, A. P.

Chemical control is the only way to arrest ShB. Resistant short-statured rice varieties need to be developed.

A program to breed high yielding varieties with ShB resistance was initiated

at AICRIP, Hyderabad, during 1979 kharif. Fifty-eight entries were field tested. Plants were inoculated by typhabit method at maximum tillering. Thirty-seven varieties were moderately resistant; scores ranged from 3.0 to 5.0. During 1980 kharif moderately resistant entries were retested in two 3.75-m rows flanked by the susceptible check variety Taichung Native 1. High humidity (RH 95%) created by overhead sprinklers induced maximum disease. Only 11 varieties showed resistant reaction (score 1.0 to 3.0) in high humidity (see table). OS4 and IR42 were scored as resistant, confirming 1979 results. IET4699 was resistant, Guyana sel. 60-283 and Pankaj were moderately resistant.

Eight thousand F₄ plants from three

crosses — RP1821 (OS4/ RPW6-I7), RP1819 (Pankaj/RP1821), and RP1822 (Pankaj/ IET5656) — were field tested under favorable conditions. RP1821 crosses were most promising — 189 plants scored highly resistant (0.0 and 1.0). Among those, 76 lines were uniform. They are being tested in a replicated yield trial at AICRIP headquarters during the 1982 dry season and at Maruteru, West Godavari, reported to be a ShB hot spot, to reconfirm disease reaction.

Tetep: a potential source of resistance to rice dwarf in Nepal

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In 1977 rice dwarf virus (RD) was discovered in Taichung 176 and KT32-2 (a locally bred line) at Khumaltar Station in Kathmandu Valley, Nepal. *Nephotetix nigropictus*, the predominant green leafhopper species in the valley, transmits the virus. To identify potential sources of RD resistance, a preliminary screening of rice cultivars was made in the greenhouse at Khumaltar during July-September 1981. We sought to

Donor screening nursery results at AICRIP, 1980 kharif.

Entries with score ^a of					
0	1	3	5	7	9
	ET4699	IR2071-588-4		IET6774	TN1
		Guyana Sel. 60-283		RP193-1	Ram Tulsi
		ET5891	T141	ARC15762	
		ET6770	Ta-poo-cho-z	IR2071-588-5	
		Pankaj	IET6234	La ka	
		IR42	IR1103-15-8		
		OS4	Nang Payah		
		ET6235	Ramadja	Phourel	
		IET6272	IET7043	Morangedo	
		Saibham	IET7109	Phekaudu	
			Athebu	Morang Chaeran	
			Mamte	Bag Murali	
			Suduwee		

^a 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale of 0-9: 0 = no incidence, 9 = lesions reaching top of tillers; severe infection on all leaves and some plants killed.

Rice dwarf and blast resistance^a of Tetep and Tetep-derived cultivars at Khumaltar, Nepal, 1977-81.

Cultivar	Rice dwarf		Rice blast	
	Diseased seedlings ^b (%)	Degree of resistance	Disease score ^c	Degree of resistance
Tetep	0	HR	0-4	MR
IR1905-8-3-1	0	HR	0-2	HR
IR1416-128-5-8	0	HR	0-1	HR
IR1544-340-6-1	20	R	0-1	HR
IR1905-PPII-29-4-61	10	R	0-1	HR

^a HR = highly resistant, R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant. ^b Av of 3 replications. ^c 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale 0-9: 0 = no incidence, 9 = 51-100%, Range is for years 1977-81.

identify a single variety resistant to RD and blast (BI), the most serious diseases in the region, to simplify breeding for resistance to both diseases.

Results indicate Tetep and lines derived from Tetep — IR 1905-8-3-1, IR1416-128-5-8 — are resistant. Tetep lines IR1544-340-6-1 and IR1905-PPII-29-4-61 were moderately resistant (disease incidence was 10-12%).

Tetep seems to be resistant to RD as well as to B1 (see table). *R*

Sources of resistance to leaf scald disease

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Leaf scald disease (LSc), caused by *Rhynchosporium oryzae*, commonly occurs in northeast India. Natural disease pressure during wet season is high and offers an excellent opportunity to screen germplasm in the field.

Since 1980, when a varietal screening program was initiated, 741 rice cultivars have been tested for LSc resistance. Few varieties have shown resistance. Of 589 cultivars evaluated in 1980, 24 were resistant. Others were moderately resistant to susceptible (see table). During 1981, 152 cultivars were tested — only 2 were resistant.

Cultivars were field-tested in upland nurseries with high nitrogen (100-60-0) fertilization. Seeds were sown in 2-m

rows at 20-cm intervals. They were surrounded by the local susceptible variety, Mirikrak, which has a susceptible to highly susceptible reaction. *R*

Field reaction of two newly released rice varieties to leaf blast and gall midge in Manipur

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In 1979, Punshi and Phouoibi, new rice varieties developed at the State Rice Research Station, Wangbal, were released in Manipur. Since release, they have almost replaced IR24, and are in about 75% of the areas planted to high yielding varieties (Punshi, 50% and Phouoibi, 25%).

Punshi, formerly KD6-18-7, is a cross between local Phouren (female parent) and IR661-1-140-3-2. It is well adapted to irrigated, rainfed lowland, and transplanted conditions and has moderate drought resistance. It is weakly photo-period sensitive and matures in 138 days. It has outyielded IR24 by 10-15% at 80-40-30 kg NPK/ha.

Phouoibi, formerly KD6-2-1, has similar parentage, adaptability, and resistance. It matures in 135 days, and has outyielded IR24 by 8-12% at 80-40-30 kg NPK/ha.

Before their release, Punshi and Phouoibi were reported to be moderately resistant to blast and gall midge, currently the most destructive local rice disease and insect pest. However, field observations and surveys conducted during July-August 1979 have hinted at high susceptibility to blast and gall

Sources of resistance to rice leaf scald, Shillong, India, 1980-81.

Variety	Score ^a		
	Upper Shillong (1800 m, 245 entries) 1980	Barapani (950 m, 152 entries) 1981	Nayabunglow (800 m, 344 entries) 1980
Paro white	—	1	1
Pokhareli masino	1	1	1
Ciat ICA-5	—	3	1
Colombia-I (73120)	—	—	1
Colombia-II	—	—	1
Aus 173	1	—	—
Carreon	1	—	—
Leng Kwang	1	—	—
PL20 (BG11-11 SEL)	1	—	—
Sail boro 56-2	1	—	—
VL8	1	—	—
Baekgogna	1	—	—
Heug Do	1	—	—
Heug Jo	1	—	—
Heug Jo Do	1	—	—
Ishikari	1	—	—
Kita-Kogane (Yukara/Joiku No. 230)	1	—	—
Nan-ei (Tomoe-Nishiki/Norin No. 20)	1	—	—
Tomoyutaka	1	—	—
Yu-Nami	1	—	—
IR9224-K 1	1	—	—
K333 (Shin-Ei/Rikuto Norin)	1	—	—
Shin-ei (Tomoe-Nishiki/Norin No. 20)	1	—	—
<i>Checks</i>			
Mirikrak (local)	5	7	9
IR36	—	7	7
IR8	7	—	5
China 1039	7	—	—

^aBy the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale 1-9: 1 = less than 1% (apical lesions), 9 = 51-100% (apical and marginal lesions).